

Heterocyclic System : I. Reaction of 4-Oxo-4H-[1]-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes with Phenylhydrazine and Formation of 1-Phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles

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Phenylhydrazine undergoes 1 : 2 addition to the aldehydic function of 4-oxo-4H-[1]-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes (I), the addition products on elimination of water giving the hydrazones (II). The latter on being refluxed in ethanolic potassium hydroxide yield 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl) pyrazoles (III). The mechanism of this transformation and the mass spectral fragmentation of the pyrazoles (III) have been discussed.

CHROMONES in their reactions with hydrazine or phenylhydrazine behave like α - β unsaturated ketones; the nucleophile attacks at C-2 (Michael addition) with concomitant opening of the pyrone ring. The intermediate thus formed undergoes further conversion to 3(5)-*o*-hydroxyphenylpyrazole system^{1,2}.

carbon of 3-formylchromones^{5,6}. The hydrazone (IIa) on being refluxed with alcoholic potassium hydroxide afforded in quantitative yield 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IIIa), m. p. 113°, UV (ethanol) : 211 nm (log ϵ 4.48) and 289 (4.22); UV (ethanol, NaOH) : 210 (3.42) and 270 (3.97); IR (nujol, cm⁻¹) : 3025 (very weak, chelated OH)⁷, 1570

It was our interest to investigate how 4-oxo-4H-[1]-benzopyran-3-carboxaldehydes (3-formylchromones) would behave towards phenylhydrazine. The present paper deals with the results of this investigation.

3-Formylchromones can be prepared either by formylating 2'-formyl-2-hydroxyacetophenones with ethyl orthoformate and acetic anhydride³ or by the application of Vilsmeier Haack reaction to various *o*-hydroxyacetophenones as prescribed by Nohara *et al.*⁴. During the present course of investigation, however, the second method⁴ was found to be most suitable.

3-Formylchromone (Ia) with phenylhydrazine gave at first a compound having m. p. 213° which did not give any colouration with ferric chloride. Its UV (ethanol) : 210 nm (log ϵ 4.16), 294 (4.16) and 345 (4.18) suggests that it has the same ring structural feature as that of the starting chromone-3-aldehyde (Ia) having UV (ethanol) : 213 (4.33), 305 (3.95) and 345 (3.96). The phenylhydrazone derivative has thus been assigned by structure (IIa). In this connection it may be noted that hydroxylamine hydrochloride as well as cyanoacetamide in presence of pyridine first attacks the aldehydic

(s, aryl pyrazolyl ketone chelated with *ortho*-OH); NMR (CDCl₃, TMS) τ : -2.87 (br. 1H, ArOH)⁸, 1.52 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₈), 1.82 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₈) and 2.05-3.20 (m, 9H, ArH); mass spectrum : 264 (M⁺, base peak), 172, 171, 144, 121, 120, 93 and 92. The structure (IIIa) was also confirmed by the following experiments. It gave violet colouration with ferric chloride. It formed an acetate, IR (nujol) cm⁻¹ : 1750 (s, ester carbonyl), 1625 (s, aryl pyrazolyl ketone), 1250 (O-acyl); NMR (CDCl₃, TMS) τ : 1.68 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₈), 1.93 (s, 1H, pyrazole H₈), 2.20-2.87 (m, 9H, ArH) and 7.85 (s, 3H, -COCH₃). On oxidation with either chromic acid in acetic acid-acetone-water at room temperature, or alkaline potassium permanganate at reflux temperature it afforded 1-phenylpyrazole-4-carboxylic acid⁸.

The formation of the pyrazole (IIIa) can be rationalised as follows : the hydroxide anion cleaves the pyrone ring of the chromone (IIa) at C-2 with the generation of an aldehyde function⁹ that further reacts with the phenylhydrazino group present in the molecule (Scheme I). Various substituted 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (III) that were similarly prepared are listed in Table 1.

TABLE 1—Melting points (in °C) of 3-formylchromones (I), their phenylhydrazones (II), 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazoles (III) and the acetates of compounds (III).

Sl. No	Substituents		Compound*	Compound†	Compound‡	Acetate of
	R	X	(I)	(II)	(III)	(III)
a	H	H	154	213	113	113
b	Me	H	170-72	—	114	114
c	H	Cl	163-65	172	145	97
d	H	Br	186	—	154	132
e	H	Me	171	210	121	—
f	H	OMe	158	207	121	—
g	Me	NO ₂	140-43	270	252	—
h	H	NO ₂	163	—	206-210	150

* Solvent of crystallisation : ethanol. Melting points of compounds (I) were very close to lit.^{a,b} m.p.s.

† Some of these compounds were not purified by crystallisation, hence their m.p.s are not recorded. Ethanol was used as solvent for crystallisation.

‡ Solvent of crystallisation was either chloroform or chloroform-pet. ether ; yield 65-80% based on comp. (I).

Scheme - I

The fragmentation patterns of 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl) pyrazoles (III) in their mass spectra are exemplified in Scheme 2 for the parent compound (IIIa).

The highly aromatic character of the compound is shown by the great intensity of the molecular ion (base peak). By electron impact, the α -carbonyl bonds are susceptible to cleavage. Thus the molecular ion can undergo fragmentation in two different ways. α -Carbonyl cleavage (A) gives two fragments

of m/e 171 and 93. By a concomitant hydrogen shift two fragments of mass units 172 and 92 are also obtained. The alternate α -carbonyl cleavage with subsequent hydrogen shift (B) produces two other fragments having m/e 144 and 120. A highly intense peak at m/e 121 is also obtained by a hydrogen shift to m/e 120 from any other ion. The m/e 144 ion may also be generated by loss of CO from the ion of m/e 172. The m/e 120 ion by elimination of CO collapses also to the ion of m/e 92.

Experimental

Formylchromones (Ia – f) were prepared from properly substituted 2-hydroxyacetophenones⁴. The experimental procedure for the preparation of 3-formylchromone (Ia) is described here as a representative case.

3-Formylchromone (Ia). N,N-dimethylformamide (45 ml) was cooled in ice-salt mixture and stirred magnetically. Phosphorus oxychloride (20 ml, 0.22 mole) was slowly added to it. Pink colour of the formylating complex appeared. *o*-Hydroxyacetophenone (13.6 g, 0.10 mole) was added drop by drop. Some time after the addition was over, the reaction mixture set to a thick mass, and it was left overnight at room temp. Next day, the semi-solid mass was decomposed by addition of water. The precipitated solid was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol to afford 3-formylchromone (Ia) (9.0 g), m.p. 154°, yield 52%.

Nitrochromones (Ig-h). These were prepared by nitrating the chromones (Ia) and (Ib) respectively^{4b}. In a typical procedure, the proper chromone (0.02 mole) was added pinch by pinch to a cooled and stirred mixture of conc. sulphuric acid (10 ml) and conc. nitric acid (10 ml). The reaction mixture was left at room temp. for 1 hr, warmed for 10 min on a water bath, and then poured in ice-water. The

solid deposited was filtered, washed with water, and recrystallised from ethanol.

Phenylhydrazones (II) of 3-formylchromones (I). A warm solution of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (0.72 g, 0.005 mole) and sodium acetate (1.40 g) in water (2-3 ml) was added at a time to formylchromone (I) (0.005 mole) dissolved in ethanol (2-3 ml) when yellow coloured hydrazone (II) separated out. The yield of the compound (II) was over 90% in each case.

1-Phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IIIa). The hydrazone (IIa) (0.50 g) was refluxed with a solution of potassium hydroxide (1.0 g) in water (2 ml) and ethanol (10 ml) for 1 hr. After cooling, the solution was diluted with water and acidified with acetic acid. The solid deposited was filtered and recrystallised from chloroform in light yellow crystals of the pyrazole (IIIa) (0.41 g), m.p. 113°. On refluxing with acetic anhydride and pyridine, it furnished an acetate, m.p. 113° (CH₃COOH).

All other hydrazones (II) were similarly converted to the pyrazoles (III).

Oxidation of 1-phenyl-4-(2-hydroxybenzoyl)pyrazole (IIIa). (a) *With chromium trioxide* :—A mixture of the compound (IIIa) (0.50 g), acetone (5 ml), acetic acid (3 ml), water (1 ml) and chromium tri-

oxide (1.0 g) were stirred magnetically at room temperature for 4 hr. It was then diluted with water and organic matter extracted with chloroform. The chloroform extract on concentration yielded *1-phenylpyrazole-4-carboxylic acid* (0.30 g), m.p. 221° (ethyl acetate – pet. ether) (lit.⁸, m.p. 219-20°). On treatment with diazomethane it gave the corresponding *methyl ester*, m.p. 127° (ethyl acetate – pet. ether) (lit.⁸, m.p. 128-9°).

(b) *With potassium permanganate* :—A mixture of the pyrazole (IIIa) (1.0 g), potassium permanganate (2 g), sodium hydroxide (3 g) and water (15 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate on acidification yielded *1-phenylpyrazole-4-carboxylic acid* (0.3 g), m.p. 221° (alcohol-water). When admixed with the chromic acid oxidation product of the pyrazole (IIIa), it melted at 221°.

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